

09 March 2026

Press Release

SUN-DT Project Unveils Visual Identity and Launches Official Website

The Horizon Europe project **SUN-DT** (“*Smart Use of Novel Digital Tools for advanced performance and reduced costs in CSP tower plants*”) has launched its visual identity and official website, marking a key step in reinforcing the visibility of both the project and Concentrated Solar Power (CSP).

Visual Identity

The visual identity centres on a logo that encapsulates the project’s core concepts. The **sun** represents the solar energy used in CSP tower plants, while the **brain icon** symbolises the “intelligence” added to CSP technology through digitalisation and advanced data processing. The **point elements** within the SUN-DT acronym represent data points, sensors, and network nodes, highlighting digital connectivity and integration of digital tools. Overall, the visual identity reinforces the goal of making CSP plants smarter and more competitive. The full set of visual identity elements, including a roll-up banner, poster and leaflet, is available in the “Public outputs” section of the project website.

Project website

The newly launched website www.sun-dt.eu provides a comprehensive overview of the project’s concept, methodology, objectives, CSP technology, demonstration activities, expected impacts, consortium partners, and public outputs. It will serve as a central hub for sharing project activities, news, and results with both technical and non-technical audiences.

About the SUN-DT project

SUN-DT will advance and integrate four innovative and interoperable digital tools into a unified **SUN-DT Platform: HELIOSTATACC** (automatic heliostat calibration and characterisation), **SUN-DTWIN** (automated decision-making of the solar field and receiver), **D-OPT** (energy management and dispatch optimisation), and **PREDOM** (predictive operation and maintenance). This platform will be tested and validated at two experimental facilities and two commercial plants, representing different CSP tower configurations.

Co-funded by
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Disclaimer:

Funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement no 101234781. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Project Information

Grant Agreement no.	101234781
Project name	Smart Use of Novel Digital Tools for advanced performance and reduced costs in CSP tower plants
Project acronym	SUN-DT
Type of action	HORIZON Innovation Actions
Topic identifier	HORIZON-CL5-2024-D3-02-01
Starting date	01 October 2025
Duration	36 months
EU contribution	€ 2.995.445,97

SUN-DT Coordinator	
CENER	FUNDACION CENER
SUN-DT Partners	
DLR	DEUTSCHES ZENTRUM FUR LUFT - UND RAUMFAHRT EV
CIEMAT	CENTRO DE INVESTIGACIONES ENERGETICAS MEDIOAMBIENTALES Y TECNOLOGICAS
IME	FUNDACION IMDEA ENERGIA
INAVITAS	INAVITAS ENERJI ANONIM SIRKETI
ACCIONA	ACCIONA CONSTRUCCION SA
COX	COX ENERGY EPC S.L.
ESTELA	EUROPEAN SOLAR THERMAL ELECTRICITY ASSOCIATION
IMN	FUNDACION IMDEA NETWORKS

To stay up-to-date on SUN-DT's activities and news, follow the project on:

- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/sun-dt/>
- X (formerly Twitter): https://x.com/SUN_DT_Project

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